

RESEARCH PROPOSAL

Greece as the continuator state of the Byzantine Republic

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Today the Greek War of Independence (1821-1829) is often discussed against the backdrop of various versions of modernization theory,¹ showcasing its connection with the Enlightenment, the Age of Revolution, and the Liberal International. The amassed evidence regarding the Byzantine/Eastern Roman identity of the 1821 Greek freedom fighters and the unceasing rebellions against the Ottoman rule before the establishment of the modern Greek state² have been consistently downplayed due to their presumed nationalistic or religious overtones as well as their utilization in the service of *Megali Idea*, i.e., the Greek irredentist foreign policy of the 19th and early 20th centuries.³ The widespread perception of Byzantium as a multiethnic theocratic empire has undoubtedly contributed to this development.

However, recent research in Byzantine studies takes a closer look at the primary sources and recounts the story of an empire that “*transformed itself from a state in which Romans ruled over non-Romans into a large, unified, and increasingly homogeneous state in which the same rights were distributed across the territory, fractally reproducing Roman social structures regardless of prior ethnicity*”.⁴ The Byzantine state is thus revealed (perhaps to the surprise of some) as a “*res publica*”⁵ based on “*consensus omnium*”⁶ and the “*rule of law*”,⁷ a “*Roman polity*” that was “*only accidentally Christian*”,⁸ a market “*predicated upon the idea of free contractual negotiation*”⁹ and yet complemented by well-organized welfare institutions.¹⁰ These insights have been considered –along with selected primary sources– in two recently published papers (the first of which is hereby submitted as a sample of my work), where I look into Byzantine and post-Byzantine society through the lens of republican

¹ See paradigmatically Diamandouros 1972.

² Sathas 1869 remains a classic.

³ See, for example, Asdrachas 2019.

⁴ Kaldellis 2019, p. 200.

⁵ Kaldellis 2015.

⁶ Beck 1994, p. 39.

⁷ Christofilopoulou 1986, p. 187.

⁸ Kaldellis 2015, p. 190.

⁹ Laiou 2002, p. 1133.

¹⁰ See, e.g., Constantelos 1968 and Miller 1997.

political theory,¹¹ and I suggest that the pioneering constitutions framed during the Greek War of Independence are a (direct or indirect) legacy of Eastern Roman republicanism.¹²

I now wish to present a more normative working hypothesis, namely that modern-day Greece –the Hellenic Republic– is the continuator state of the Byzantine Republic. From this point of view, the Ottoman rule was a prolonged illegal occupation, and its end entailed the restoration of Byzantine sovereignty albeit in a new form; it is one of these cases “*where the ‘same’ State can be said to continue to exist despite sometimes drastic changes in its government, its territory or its people*”.¹³

How can we prove this hypothesis? One way would be to demonstrate the existence of rudimentary state organs. The arrival of Thomas Palaiologos in Rome in 1460 could be described as the formation of “*a Byzantine government in exile*”,¹⁴ while the continued use of titles like “*Emperor of Constantinople*,” “*Despot of the Morea*,” or “*Despot of Epirus*” may suggest that the corresponding offices were seen as vacant or disputed, but nonetheless still existing.¹⁵ Furthermore, I have tried to explain in a forthcoming paper how the polity of the Maniots turned from a rump state of the Byzantine Republic to the matrix of the First Hellenic Republic.¹⁶

A different approach would be to affirm the republican argument that preserving cultural identity is an effective means of protecting state continuity. If, for instance, the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe was urging “*member Governments to support appropriate efforts of Baltic refugees to maintain their natural culture traditions and languages, in anticipation of the time when Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania*” would shake off Soviet rule,¹⁷ what stops us from seeing the Christian faith of Ottoman Greeks not as an obstacle to political freedom but as its safeguard?¹⁸

This is the sort of concerns that can arise out of this provocative hypothesis, and the academic community of the Center for Hellenic Studies would be an ideal place to raise them. After all, even if these assumptions can be corroborated, what conclusions could we draw from them? Would they serve purposes of truth and reconciliation, or not? The present proposal forms part of a comprehensive attempt at revisiting the role of the Byzantine past in the formation of modern Greece and rediscovering the indigenous republican tradition of the Eastern Mediterranean. This long-term project involves more than just the papers mentioned above. It also includes my doctoral research on the legal and

¹¹ Koutoufaris-Malandrinos 2022.

¹² Koutoufaris-Malandrinos 2023.

¹³ Crawford 2006, pp. 667-668.

¹⁴ Angold 2014, p. 105.

¹⁵ Harris 2013.

¹⁶ Koutoufaris-Malandrinos (forthcoming).

¹⁷ PACE 1960.

¹⁸ That was exactly the point made by Dimitrios Katartzis: “*Whence we constitute a nation in which our ecclesiastical rulers bind us to the supreme administration and among ourselves. In many respects, our ecclesiastical rulers are also our political rulers; many of our political laws, which are named âdet (customs), and all our ecclesiastical laws which are named ayin (religion), draw validity from their self-governing power*” (Katartzis 1999, p. 44, as translated in Molos 2019, p. 52).

political thought of Athanasios Christopoulos (1772-1847), a jurist trained in Byzantine law and a famous poet active in the milieu of the Danubian Principalities, i.e., the “*Byzantium after Byzantium*” par excellence.¹⁹

This proposal deals with international law, operates in the context of a republican reading of Greek history, and insists on the importance of court titles, local institutions, and culture as indicators of state continuity. In other words, it is situated at the intersection of at least two research topics of this program (Political Theory and International Relations, Greek Language and Culture) while simultaneously providing a framework for posing questions related to other topics (e.g., Architecture and Urban Design).²⁰

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¹⁹ Iorga 2000.

²⁰ For example, could the denial of the Byzantine republican tradition explain the classicizing transformation of the monumental landscape in post-1831 Greece?

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